

Establishment of a Rapid Screening Method for Drought Tolerance of Rice Genotypes at Seedling Stage

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ABSTRACT

Lack of accurate screening techniques is a limiting factor to develop rice cultivars tolerant to drought, which is the most important constraint in rice productivity. Three experiments were conducted to establish a screening method, and to screen drought tolerant rice genotypes at seedling stage. First, two soil mixtures (2:1 and 3:1) with steady drying slope were selected for screening. Second, three rice genotypes were evaluated in nursery trays *in vivo*, showing higher stress in soil mixture 2:1 than in 3:1. Genotype KHS7 exhibited the highest resistance, while TS2 showed the least. A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.9156$; $p < 0.0001$) was found between percentage of soil water content and leaf drying. Third, *in vitro* evaluation of three genotypes under polyethylene glycol (PEG) induced stress demonstrated TCS17 with a higher tolerance to drought over TNGS14 and CSY112. Thus, a rapid, simple, and feasible technique which combines the use of nursery trays and polyethylene glycol (PEG) tissue culture test was developed to select drought tolerant rice genotypes at seedling stage under controlled conditions.

Key words: drought tolerance, rice genotypes, screening, seedling stage

Introduction

Drought is the most widespread constraint in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) production affecting grain yield and quality (Mostajeran and Rahimi-Eichim, 2009). Rice yield losses due to drought stress have been estimated to reach up to 58% (Ouk *et al.*, 2006). Valuable differences exist in grain yield between drought-prone rice production systems (uplands and rainfed lowlands) and irrigated ones (Fukai *et al.*, 1999). For example, drought-prone systems represent over half of the world area dedicated to grow rice, but represent only 25% of the total world rice production (Venuprasad, Lafitte, and Atlin, 2007). In lowland irrigated systems, high yielding varieties reach an averaged productivity around 6 to 8 t ha⁻¹, while in rainfed systems adapted varieties produce hardly around 1 t ha⁻¹ (Prasad, 2011). Additionally, water scarcity, which is becoming a serious problem with global climate changes, is a potential risk for rice productivity and food security (Li *et al.*, 2011). The percentage of drought-affected land area has doubled from 1970's to 2000's and, unfortunately, the future trend seems to be similar (Mostajeran and Rahimi-Eichim, 2009). In Asia, where 90% of the world's rice is produced and consumed (Hibberd *et al.*, 2008), it is estimated that by 2025, 15 million hectares of traditionally irrigated land will suffer physical water scarcity and 22 million hectares will be under economic water scarcity (Prasad, 2011).

The development of new rice genotypes tolerant to drought stress will increase and stabilize yield, and could save water (Zhou *et al.*, 2006). The availability of landraces represents a powerful source of adapted drought tolerance genes donors for breeding (Kumar *et al.*, 2009; Thomson *et al.*, 2010). Unfortunately, these genotypes, normally, have many undesirable agronomic traits and low yield potential (Thomson *et al.*, 2010). Thus, the challenge for rice breeders is to combine robust drought tolerant cultivars with high yielding trait. However, development of drought tolerant rice cultivars has been hindered by unpredictable drought occurrence (Venuprasad, Lafitte, and Atlin, 2007), difficulties in defining target environment, complex genotype x environment interaction and lack of reliable methodology to screen large number of genotypes in breeding programs (Kamoshita *et al.*, 2008; Lafitte *et al.*, 2006).

Drought stress causes serious deleterious effects on plant metabolic processes, including water relations, nutrient uptake and photosynthetic assimilates (Xiong *et al.*, 2012). Drought resistance in rice mainly depends on the capacity for osmotic adjustment, allowing plants to maintain turgor and to control water loss (Sato and Yokoya, 2008). Drought occurrence at early stages, such as seedling, results in poor crop

establishment and reduces number of panicles per area and the panicle size (Li and Xu, 2007). Screening for drought tolerance in rice at seedling stage have been reported (Basu *et al.*, 2010; Cui *et al.*, 2008; Gorantla *et al.*, 2007; Kato *et al.*, 2008; Zhou *et al.*, 2006). On the other hand, physical soil property is an important factor for drought selection that needs to be considered (Cairns *et al.*, 2011).

In vitro techniques, such as tissue culture, provide useful tools for crop breeding. In drought stress (like in other abiotic stress), *in vitro* alternatives offer the opportunity to mimic the field condition using a chemical stressing agent in the medium. Uses of *in vitro* screening help to increase the selection efficiency and to screen large numbers of genotypes in controlled conditions, and to save time with a relatively low cost (Rai *et al.*, 2011). High molecular weight polyethylene glycol (PEG) mimics drought stress in plants as a non-penetrating osmotic agent, reducing the water potential similar to soil drying (Anithakumari *et al.*, 2011; Rai *et al.*, 2011). Kulkarni and Deshpande (2007) reported an *in vitro* methodology to screen a large set of tomato germplasm using PEG. Also, Anithakumari *et al.* (2011) used PEG as stressing agent create the first “*in vitro* screening of a mapping population for drought tolerance in potato”.

In rice, PEG has been used to simulate osmotic stress Kato *et al.* (2008) found PEG as an effective treatment to analyze drought tolerance at seedling stage in a hydroponic culture. Similarly, Zhou *et al.* (2006) used PEG in a glass tube to identify quantitative trait loci (QTL) related to drought tolerance in rice seedling. However, an appropriate methodology for evaluating drought tolerance must be simple, operable and accurate (Zhou *et al.*, 2006).

The aim of this study was to establish an accurate screening technique to evaluate rice drought tolerant genotypes at seedling stage both *in vivo* and *in vitro* conditions. Also, to test combinationa of apropiate soil mixture in rice seedling nursery tray, and polyethylene glycol (PEG) as st ressing agent added to the media in tissue culture, which can be used to evaluate genotypic variation in rice tolerance to drought at early stage.

Materials and Methods

Three experiments were conducted to evaluate rice drought tolerance at National Pingtung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan, between August and October 2011. Two of them were done in greenhouse (*in vivo*): first, the selection of an appropriate soil mixture for drought tolerance screening in nursery trays for rice seedlings, and, second, the evaluation of rice genotypes using those

selected soil mixtures. Finally, rice genotypes were screened under *in vitro* osmotic stress simulated using polyethylene glycol (PEG). Each experiment was replicated three times. The first experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The second and third experiments were designed as split-split plot and two-factorial complete randomized design (CRD), respectively.

Plant Materials

Five rice genotypes were evaluated; one inbreeds line (CSY112), and four commercial Taiwanese varieties - Kaohsiung Sen 7 (KHS7), Tai Sen 2 (TS2), Taichung Sen 17 (TCS17), and Tainung Sen 14 (TNGS14). These genotypes were provided by Kaohsiung District Agricultural Research and Extension Station. CSY112 was identified as drought sensitive in preliminary studies, and TCS17 as higher drought tolerant. On the other hand, TNGS14 showed intermediate responses to drought stress. Thus, TNGS14 was selected as a common reference genotype for *in vivo* and *in vitro* screening at seedling stage.

Physical Properties Test on Soil Mixtures for Drought Tolerance Screening

This experiment was conducted in greenhouse to define the drying slope pattern of different soil mixtures in rice

seedling nursery-trays. The greenhouse averaged maximum temperature during the experiment was $32.31^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2.69$, and the averaged minimum temperature was $24.58^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.64$. The nursery trays were 58 cm long, 28 cm wide and 3 cm depth; and were soil filled up to 2.6 cm depth reaching a volume of 0.0042 m^3 each one. Five soil mixtures were studied as a soil:sand ratio (0:1, 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 and 1:0). The soil particles were separated using a laboratory test sieve shaker (Retsch®; Haan, Germany), following the USDA classification system (Gee and Or, 2002) to state the proportion of soil:sand particles used (Table 1).

Nursery trays (experimental units) containing the mixtures were well irrigated for two days. Then, drought was started withholding irrigation; the drying period lasted 12 days. Soil samples were collected daily from each experimental unit to calculate soil mass water content (MWC) using gravimetric moisture content method. These soil samples were weighed in their container (W_w) and oven dried for 24 hours at 110°C to get the soil dry weight (W_d). Later, the weight of the container (W) was subtracted. The soil mass water content was calculated following the equation, as referred by Zeng (1993):

$$\text{MWC} = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_d - w} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Physical Properties of the Five Soil Mixtures¹

Soil mixtures	Sand	Silt	Clay
0:1	39.9	35.5	24.5
1:1	20.8	24.3	54.9
2:1	14.2	22.2	63.6
3:1	12.5	16.8	70.7
1:0	0.8	5.8	93.4

¹ Particle Size Distribution calculated according to the USDA classification system (sandy <2000 µm to 500; silt <500 µm to 200 µm; clay < 200 µm).

In Vivo Screening of Rice Seedling for Drought Tolerance

Three rice genotypes (KHS7, TS2 and TNGS14) were evaluated for drought tolerance at seedling stage in greenhouse using nursery trays. The seedlings were grown in nursery trays with two different mixtures of soil:sand ratio (2:1 and 3:1) selected from the previous experiment. Mature rice seeds were germinated on the nursery trays and irrigated for three days. Then, for the drought stressed treatment the irrigation was stopped, while control treatment was irrigated daily.

Leaf relatively water content (RWC), plant height and leaf drying (LD) sensitivity were measured for each treatment. To determine RWC (González and González-Vilar, 2003), leaf samples were collected from 12 days old seedlings and weighed to get fresh weight (*FW*). Then, the samples were floated on water at 4°C to get saturated weight (*SW*), and later, oven dried at 70°C for 24 hours

and weighed (*DW*). RWC was calculated as follows:

$$RWC = \frac{FW - DW}{SW - DW} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Leaf drying was visually measured on 12, 15, and 18 days old seedlings, following the description by IRRI's Standard Evaluation System for rice (SES). The score range is from 0 to 9; '0' indicating not visible dry symptoms and '9' indicating all leaf dead (IRRI, 2002).

In Vitro Screening of Rice Seedlings for Drought Tolerance

Three rice genotypes (CSY112, TCS17, and TNGS14) were evaluated for drought tolerance using polyethylene glycol (PEG-6000) *in vitro*. Ethanol (75%) and sodium hypochlorite (3%) were used sequentially to sterilize the surface of dehusked mature rice seeds. A drop of polysorbate surfactant was added to the sodium hypochlorite. After sterilization,

the seeds were rinsed three times with RO-system purified water. Then, sterilized seeds were cultured for germination in Petri Dish containing MS basal medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). Afterward, germinated seedlings larger than 2 mm were sub cultured in 500 ml flask containing MS basal medium for control treatment or MS basal medium added with 5 g l⁻¹ of polyethylene glycol – PEG (6000) for drought stressed treatment. Sucrose (30 g l⁻¹) and agar (7 g l⁻¹; Difco™ Agar, BD; France) were used as carbon source and gelling agent, respectively, and 2 mg l⁻¹ of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) were added. The tissue culture room temperature was 25°C±2; relative humidity around 70% and light intensity with a light period of 16/8 hrs. Survival rate percentage in relation to the control, fresh weight (FW), and dry weight (DW) of seedlings were evaluated. Seedlings were dried 24 hours at 70°C to get the dry weight (DW). Percentage of dry matter (DM) content was estimated using the following equation (Mohamed and Tawfik, 2006):

$$DM = \frac{DW}{FW} \times 100. \quad (3)$$

Statistical Analysis

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS 9.1 software. The least significant differences (LSD at p = 0.05%) test was used to define significant differences among

treatment means. For survival rate, chi-squared was calculated.

Results and Discussion

Physical Properties of Soil Mixtures for Drought Screening

The drying slope pattern of five soil:sand mixtures was identified in greenhouse. The results showed that soil mass water moisture decreased progressively in different soil mixtures to a range from 20% to 45% on the first day after irrigation was stopped (Figure 1). Twelve days later, all soil mixtures reached a mass water content around 2% to 4%. A relative fast drying process during the beginning few days was noticed. However, from day 3 to 6 after drought treatment, a steady decline of water content was observed for all treatments.

As expected, 1:0 ratio soil:sand mixture retained the highest soil water content, showing the capacity of clay particles to retain moisture, which plays an important role in drought stress screening (Cairns et al., 2011). The 3:1 soil mixture showed the second highest soil water content, and the mixture at 1:1 the lowest. These findings provided the drying pattern of different soil mixtures, which helped to predict the soil moisture for screening drought tolerance in rice seedling using nursery trays. Thus, the treatments with steady decline (2:1 and 3:1) were selected for screening in next stage.

Figure 1. Pattern of Drying Slope curve in Mass Water Content of Five Soil Mixtures

In Vivo Screening of Rice Seedlings for Drought Tolerance

The responses of three rice genotypes at seedling stage in greenhouse were evaluated in drought stressed and well watered conditions, combined with two soil mixtures (2:1 and 3:1). Leaf relative water content (RWC), plant height, and leaf drying (LD) were recorded.

Soil water condition in nursery trays showed an important influence on RWC and plant height of rice seedling, which decreased dramatically under drought stressed treatments in all genotypes (Table 2). Kaohsiung Sen 7 (KHS7) maintained the highest RWC in both

drought stressed and non-stressed environments. However, no significant differences among genotypes were observed in RWC. Although the highest RWC was found at 2:1 soil combination ratio in well watered treatments, no differences among soil mixtures was found under drought stress conditions.

On the other hand, plant height was found significant different among water conditions and genotypes. The three genotypes had a similar height in well watered environment. Significant reduction in height under drought stress was noted, in which KHS7 had largest reduction plant height to drought under drought stress (Table 3).

Table 2. Analysis of Relative Water Content, and Plant Height and Leaf Drying of Rice Seedling under Different Water Conditions and Soil Mixtures¹

Water conditions	Soil mixtures ²	RWC (%)	Height (cm)	LD (12DOS)	LD (15DOS)	LD (18DOS)
Watered	2:1	88.66±3.06a ³	20.00±1.13a ³	0.0±0.0a ⁴	0.0±0.0a ³	0.0±0.0a ³
	3:1	72.87±8.00b	19.38±1.12a	0.0±0.0a	0.0±0.0a	0.0±0.0a
Drought ⁵	2:1	10.45±0.87c	12.07±2.99b	1.67±1.32b	5.00±2.06b	8.67±0.71c
	3:1	10.49±1.24c	10.67±2.89b	0.22±0.44a	3.44±2.01b	7.89±0.93b

¹ Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different according to LSD multiple comparisons.

² Soil mixtures as in Table 1. RWC - relative water content; LD – leaf drying and DOS – days old seedlings.

³ p<0.01.

⁴ p<0.0001.

⁵ Irrigation was stopped at three days old seedling.

Table 3. Relative Water Content and Plant Height of 12 Days Old Different Rice Genotypes Seedling under Different Water Conditions¹

Water conditions	Genotypes	RWC (%) ²	Height (cm)
Watered	KHS7	84.58±8.50a ³	19.10±0.45a ³
	TS2	78.30±13.35b	19.40±1.36a
	TNGS14	79.43±8.02b	20.57±0.95a
Drought	KHS7	11.47±0.47c	8.23±1.30c
	TS2	10.39±0.94c	11.93±2.01b
	TNGS14	9.59±0.61c	13.93±1.89b

¹ Means in RWC and Height columns followed by different are significantly different according to LSD multiple comparison.

² RWC – relative water content.

³ p< 0.0001.

In terms of leaf drying (LD), no drying symptoms were observed in well watered treatment. The data with 12, 15, and 18 days old seedlings showed that leaf drying tends to be higher at soil:sand combination 2:1 than at combination 3:1 (Table 4). Different drought sensitivities were found among genotypes. KHS7 showed less death of leaves throughout the scoring process, even with 18 days old seedlings. The highest rate of leaf drying was found in genotype TS2, in which all leaves were dead when the seedlings reached 18 days old.

Relative water content and leaf drying are measured in plant stress studies to estimate the water status of the plants, and it varies among rice genotypes under drought stress (Lafitte, 2002). In our results, even though differences among genotypes in LD were noticed in drought stress, rice genotypes had similar RWC under drought stress. This could be due to the dryness level of the young leave tissue. Earlier record of the RWC could provide opportunities to indentify the different response of rice genotypes seedling to water status in drought conditions.

Overall, a strong negative correlation ($r=-0.9156$; $p<0.0001$) was found between percentage of soil water content and leaf drying (Figure 2). This relationship confirms leaf drying as a consistent selection criterion to evaluate plant water status of rice seedling under drought stress.

According to these results, leaf drying can be successfully used to evaluate drought tolerance in rice genotypes at seedling stage grown in nursery trays. Genotypes were more affected differently by drought stress in soil combination 3:1 than in soil combination 2:1. This finding confirms the importance of soil physical properties for evaluating the response of plants to water scarcity (Cairns *et al.*, 2011). As a result, for an appropriate *in vivo* screening method for drought tolerance, the physical properties of soil should be considered in field experiments.

In this test, KHS7 showed the best drought resistance, while TS2 was least resistant. However, KHS7 showed the highest decreasing in seedling height, which could be a tolerance strategy. Additionally, KHS7 remained greener than the other two varieties, which suggest that this variety can remain a better water status under drought conditions although its growth was reduced.

In Vitro Screening of Rice Seedling for Drought Tolerance

The response of survival rate, fresh weight, dry weight and dry matter on drought-stressed rice genotypes at seedling stage *in vitro* were evaluated. Chi-squared analysis of the survival rate showed that there is clear relationship between survival rate and genotypes,

Table 4. Leaf Drying of Three Rice Genotypes under Drought Stress in Two Soil Combination Treatments¹

Genotypes	Soil mixtures	12 DOS ²	15 DOS	18 DOS
KHS7	2:1	0.67±0.58ab ³	3.67±2.31ab ⁴	8.33±1.15ab ⁴
	3:1	0.00±0.00a	1.33±0.58a	7.0±0.00a
TS2	2:1	2.00±1.73ab	6.0±2.65b	9.0±0.00b
	3:1	0.33±0.58ab	5.33±1.15b	8.67±0.58b
TNGS14	2:1	2.33±1.15b	5.33±0.58b	8.50±0.71b
	3:1	0.33±0.58ab	3.67±1.53ab	8.00±1.00ab

¹ The leaf drying score range was from 0 to 9; '0' indicating not visible dry symptoms while '9' indicating all leaf dead (IRRI, 2002). Means followed by different letters following within each column are statistically different according to LSD multiple comparison.

² DOS – days old seedling.

³ p<0.01.

⁴ p<0.0001.

Figure 2. Correlation between Percentage of Soil Water Content and Leaf Drying

where differences among genotypes were observed (Table 5). Genotype TCS17 showed the highest survival rate under stress (93.33%), meanwhile TNGS14 showed the lowest survival rate (63.33%). The genotypes CSY112 kept 70% of survival rate under stress compared to the control treatment. That is to say that drought stress treatment reduced the survival rate by 6.67, 30 and 36.67% in genotypes TCS17, CSY112 and TNGS14, respectively.

Also, the addition of 5 g l⁻¹ of high molecular weight PEG (6000) to solid agar medium reduced fresh weight in comparison to the control, and significant differences among genotypes were observed (Figure 3). For fresh weight, genotype TCS17 showed no significant reduction between control and stressed treatment; however, significant reduction was observed in genotypes CSY112 and TNGS 14. The tendency in the response in dry weight was similar to the response in fresh weight for each genotype (Figure 4). Previous *in vitro* screening also reported similar decreasing results on plant cell growth when PEG is supplemented on tissue culture media (Aazami, Torabu, and Jalili, 2010; Biswas *et al.*, 2002; Joshi, Shukla, and Sairam, 2011).

Unlike fresh and dry weigh, the percentage of dry matter (DM) consistently increased under PEG treatment, but not statistically significant; although TCS17 tend to have higher increase of DM under stress (Figure 5). Similarly, increased percentage of DM

has been observed in plants as a result of osmotic stress, resulting in a decrease of water content in the plant tissues (Aazami, Torabu, and Jalili, 2010).

Results in this experiment suggested that screening *in vitro*, using polyethylene glycol (PEG-6000) as stressing agent, is a practical methodology to analyze and select rice genotypes for drought tolerance at seedling stage. The genotype TCS17 was found to have better performance under drought stress, maintaining higher and stable survival rate, fresh weight and dry weight than others genotypes. Unlikely, CSY112 and TNGS14 were found to be the most susceptible to drought stress.

Conclusions

Two drought screening techniques to evaluate rice genotypes at seedling stage were enhanced. Both *in vivo* and *in vitro* approaches provide operable and accurate evaluation for rice drought tolerance at seedling stage. For *in vivo* screening, an accurate and simple method was develop, using nursery trays, to select drought tolerant rice genotypes at seedling stage in greenhouse. For *in vitro* screening, genotypic variation was identified in rice seedling tolerance to PEG-induced drought in the tissue culture medium. Besides, the drying pattern slope of five soil mixtures with different physic properties was defined. Understanding this pattern could help to optimize *in vivo* screening of genotypes for drought tolerance in breeding programs.

Table 5. Survival Rate of Three Rice Genotypes under Drought Stress Condition in Vitro

		Survival rate ¹	
		Dead	Survived
Genotypes	CSY112	30.00%	70.00%
	TCS17	6.67%	93.33%
	TNGS14	36.67%	63.33%

Figure 3. Fresh Weight of Three Rice Genotypes under Drought Stress at Seedling Stage

Figure 4. Dry Weight of Three rice Genotypes under Drought Stress at Seedling Stage

Figure 5. Dry Matter of Three Rice Genotypes under Drought Stress at Seedling Stage

Applications of these techniques provide appropriate tools for breeding programs to select drought tolerant rice genotypes. Furthermore, these approaches enable breeders to screen any time of the year with reduced time, and reduced dependence on unpredictable drought season to select in the field.

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